

THE ROLE OF TEACHERS IN FORMING THE SKILLS OF COMMUNICATION DURING THE SCHOOL PERIOD

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Abstract: This article talks about the role of teachers in the formation of communicative speech in school education. A structure, model of formation of communicative competence has been developed, and it is based on the principles of activity and consistency, taking into account the educational and social experience of students, active methods of teaching.

Keywords: speech, skill, speech development, anatomical condition, physiological condition, psychological condition, declensions, conjugations.

Human speech develops gradually, the process of speech development consists of several stages. In the first year of a child's life, anatomical, physiological and psychological conditions are created for the acquisition of speech. This stage of speech development is preparation, before speech. A child in the second year of life practically learns human speech. But this speech is grammatical in nature - although the child is already building sentences, there are no declensions, conjugations, prepositions and conjunctions. Grammatically correct oral speech is formed in the third year of a child's life, but even at this stage, the child makes many mistakes in morphology and word formation. In middle and senior preschool years, further development of speech takes place, and by the age of seven, by the time the child enters school, he has sufficiently mastered the system of his native language and is fluent in spoken, oral speech. [2, 69]

Studying at school leads to great changes in the development of a child's speech. These shifts are due to the fact that the child's speech is subject to new requirements associated with learning many new academic subjects. For school-age children, speech is a means of practical communication with other people, and in the process of its formation, later in school-age children, speech is also a means of mastering the knowledge system. Without learning the language itself, learning literacy - reading and writing, it is clear that the child's speech cannot fulfill the task of systematic and comprehensive knowledge of reality. Therefore, the child's spoken language becomes his special subject of study in the learning environment. The student studies three aspects of language: phonetic, lexical and grammatical. [5, 56]

In the process of language learning, all types of students' speech are improved and developed. Development of written language. Especially the written speech has more value in the development of the student's speech. A person who knows the written language well will have much more opportunities to communicate. A student who has mastered written language can express and convey his thoughts in writing to a non-literate person. Similarly, by using written language, he can learn other people's opinions and most importantly, he can gain knowledge by reading textbooks and other books.[1, 128]

The student's written speech is much more demanding than his oral speech. The written presentation of this or that educational material must be strictly coherent and coherent, understandable to the student. At this stage, the synthesis of letters into syllables and syllables into words is slow and with certain difficulties. This is explained by the following psychological reasons: firstly, since the student has not yet been able to distinguish the graphic style of letters well, their recognition is slow and erroneous; secondly, the learner has difficulty connecting letters with corresponding sounds and often makes mistakes. As a result, there is a delay in the synthesis of word elements and poor recognition.

In the second stage - synthetic - the student synthesizes the elements of the word without much difficulty and faster. However, even at this stage there are mistakes in the synthesis of the word. They are the result of the rush of schoolchildren to study before distinguishing the constituent elements of the word, that is, by guessing. Often, these errors occur when the word being read looks like another familiar word.

At the third stage - analytic-synthetic - the reading process of schoolchildren is based on the rapid differentiation and combination of word elements. This is the stage of fluent and accurate reading.

The speed of reading increases significantly from class to class. For example, a first grader who finishes priming reads aloud about three times slower than a fourth grader, who in turn reads twice as slowly as a tenth grader. Meaningful, "thinking" reading relies on the development of complex thought processes that ensure understanding of the main and important points of the text content. Meaningful reading is not given immediately, but develops gradually, in the process of education and upbringing. The teacher should know both the reasons that prevent the development of reading and the tools that accelerate its development.

The experience of working at school and psychological research show that the misunderstanding of a certain text by young students is due to the poor vocabulary of children, the fact that they cannot find the main idea when they read, connect individual parts of the text. depends on whether or not. Eliminating these shortcomings in the development of meaningful reading requires a special effort from the teacher. First of all, it is necessary to develop and enrich children's vocabulary. And for this, it is important to know what kind of vocabulary the child has and how well these words express the content of the concepts. Schoolchildren should be taught to find the main idea of a story or a passage from a textbook. important words and sentences that express this idea. For this, children are taught to plan the story they read, to look for the most correct titles of stories, paragraphs, parts of the plan, etc. Expressive reading of the text by the teacher, and then by the students themselves; it helps a lot to understand the content of the text being read. Expressive reading reveals the semantic content of the text with the help of lively intonation, logical emphasis. [8, 45]

O'qish ko'nikmalarini egallash bilan deyarli bir vaqtda yozish ko'nikmalarini egallash ham sodir bo'ladi. Agar o'qish ko'nikmalarini o'zlashtirganda, bola harflardan tovushlarga o'tadigan bo'lsa, u holda yozish ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish teskari tartibda, ya'ni tovushlardan harflarga o'tadi. Yozuv malakalarini shakllantirish uch bosqichdan o'tadi.

Almost simultaneously with the acquisition of reading skills is the acquisition of writing skills. If a child moves from letters to sounds when learning reading skills, then the formation of writing skills goes in the opposite order, that is, from sounds to letters. The formation of writing skills goes through three stages.

In the first stage - the beginning - the child's attention is mainly focused on writing elements of letters, standing correctly, hand movements, using a pencil and a notebook.

In the second stage - verbatim - when the actions related to writing the elements of letters and the technical rules of writing are gradually automated and become easy for the child, his attention turns to the correct representation of the letters. In the third stage, coherent writing skills are formed. Here, the student's attention is focused on the correct addition of letters to words, and the fulfillment of the requirements of writing the letters themselves in terms of size, slope, pressure, position and position on the ruler.

According to their psychological nature, spelling errors in junior high school students are of two types: habitual errors and errors of ignorance. A younger student's letter is dominated by errors of ignorance. For errors caused by ignorance, in contrast to usual errors, their instability is characteristic: today the student writes the word like this, tomorrow - differently. Errors caused by ignorance are easier to overcome than common errors. After the child has firmly mastered the spelling rules of a certain category of words, errors caused by ignorance are eliminated. This is often not enough for common mistakes, and more training is required so that the child can strengthen the correct spelling of the word and write it automatically to a certain extent.

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